

Effect Of Patient Education In Family Medicine Practices

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: June 20, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July 09, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Education, Family Medicine , Health Education</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5112133</p>	<p><i>Family medicine is the nucleus of medicine and the first line of defense in light of the increase in various health problems, and the doctor can increase his chance of advancement in his work and increase his ability to confront various health problems by obtaining the necessary skills and experience in the field of health education for patients. Health education has become one of the most important factors for raising awareness in society about health problems and common diseases and their prevention, in addition to identifying the types of medical errors and how to prevent them, in addition to achieving patient safety goals and other important standards and goals. Through this research, we will learn about the concept of health education and the concept of family medicine and find the relationship between them by answering the main research question: What is the impact of health education on family medicine practices? Regarding to the study methodology, the descriptive analytical method will be relied upon in order to review previous studies. The results will be discussed and suggestions made for developing family practices strategies that will contribute to building healthy impacts in the community and changing wrong behaviors, which contributes to preventing and reducing the spread of diseases.</i></p>

Introduction

Patient education has become an urgent and crucial health necessity because it constitutes the first and strongest lines of defense and through which the well-known saying (prevention is better than treatment) is realized. Patient education in this sense is people's knowledge of health information and facts and their sense of responsibility towards their health and the health of others and translating this into practical application, instead of remaining the health information as a theoretical information only (DeMarco, Nystrom, & Salvatore, 2011).

There is a strong relationship between family medicine practices and the concept of patient education. Physicians working in the field of family medicine help spread health education. Health education or patient education is a combination of scientifically studied health experiences designed to help individuals and communities (DeMarco, Nystrom, & Salvatore, 2011).

To improve their health status by increasing health knowledge and confronting health crises experienced by societies, and health initiatives can help in this either by focusing on improving current medical problems or through education (preventive training), Instructing people on how to live with the disease through educational and activities planned by health professionals, and identifying the wrong behaviors that may lead to many diseases (Wittink & Oosterhaven, 2018).

It is the responsibility of administrators and doctors in family medicine practices to educate patients and their families, many educational services can be provided in the following areas: Child safety and injury prevention programs

Educating about basic first aid and educating parents and caregivers about how to act in the following situations: broken bones and wounds, choking, swallowing foreign objects or batteries, Drowning [including practical CPR], poisoning, burns (Wittink & Oosterhaven, 2018).

Prenatal education, In partnership with Clinical Services for Women, they can promote the health and well-being of expectant mothers and their babies. Topics include, but are not limited to: healthy eating, physical activity, emotional health, and breastfeeding (DeMarco, Nystrom, & Salvatore, 2011).

Educating children and their families about diabetes

By educating and empowering patients and their families through individual and group educational sessions on diabetes management and the consequences of neglecting treatment (DeMarco, Nystrom, & Salvatore, 2011).

Health awareness campaigns

This is done by promoting health by raising awareness about important health issues for patients through awareness campaigns. Including Diabetes Day, Asthma Day, Breastfeeding Week, Autism Day, Breast Cancer Day, Oral Health Day, smoking cessation and more (DeMarco, Nystrom, & Salvatore, 2011).

Research Aims As Well As Questions

Objectives of the research include the following:

- 1- Demonstrate a critical knowledge of patient education.
- 2- Discuss the definition and concept of patient education and define its objectives.
- 3- Comparison of the two primary ways of delivering the health message.
- 4- Identify some areas of patient education particularly in the field of family practices.
- 5- Determining the components of patient education and the specifications that should be available in the message.
- 6- Determine the skills that a patient educator must acquire.
- 7- Determining the information that the patient educator must know in order to develop the best practices of family medicine.
- 8- Provide a clear knowledge about the positive impacts of patient education in family medicine practices.

Questions include the following:

- 1- What is the patient education?
- 2- What are the elements of health education?
- 3- What is the family medicine practices?
- 4- What is the effect of patient education in family medicine practices.

Methodology

I used books, research articles, and reports from Google Scholar, Search gate, SpringerLink, as well as Emerald to successfully cover the previously specified areas. Any previous studies that examined another topic or another relation will be rejected. I have concentrated my research on the subject of the research, which is "Effect of patient education in family medicine practices". The descriptive analytical method will be relied upon in order to review previous studies.

Literature review

Concept of patient education

It refers to an educational process that provides people with the necessary knowledge about health and its determinants, disease and ecology (host, causative agent and environment), pathological manifestations, methods of treatment and prevention, and seeks to promote positive attitudes towards health and healthy behaviors, and can lead to the acquisition of healthy practices.

There are purposes of patient education, these purposes are:

- knowledge: increasing people's interest in health, about the health problems of society (definition, manifestations, treatment and prevention).
- Attitude: Promote positive attitudes.
- Practice: motivating and teaching proper healthy behavior.

There are many areas of the patient education, one of the most important of which is personal and general hygiene, nutritional, infection awareness, Harmful behavior and accidents, Lifestyle. There are components of patient education, the components are five basic components are the sender, receiver, the message, method, impact (Przybylska, Borzęcki, Drop, Przybylski, & Drop, 2014).

With regard to the qualities that must be available in a patient educator, they are as follows, knowledge, experience and awareness. Communication ability (possessing communication skills). patience. A person who is close to society (and if he is a stranger to society, he must know the information previously explained). Possesses the necessary qualifications to be a good model by practicing healthy behaviours (Przybylska, Borzęcki, Drop, Przybylski, & Drop, 2014).

Physicians in the field of family medicine should know what information they should learn about the people they want to educate? Like the customs and traditions of the community. Economic and social conditions. Educational level. Age and gender. Occupation. Health status (Jimbo, 2004).

It is important to have the following in the health message, to be clear understandable. Easy to apply. proportionate to age and gender. Realistic and based on accurate scientific foundations. Objective and avoids the means of amplification and intimidation (Jimbo, 2004).

There are methods of patient education, there are methods that rely on the media, the methods depend on the personal interview. Among the important methods are the following, advice, for example, when someone

feels a problem and comes to the educator and asks for advice. The steps required of the patient educators here are: Securing the appropriate place and time (to be followed by securing confidentiality and privacy): for example, A child with a problem of sexual abuse cannot be counseled in the classroom in front of his colleagues or in the administration in front of the teachers (Jimbo, 2004) (DeMarco, Nystrom, & Salvatore, 2011).

Find out information about the person: the question. listening. Build a comprehensive picture of the situation (from asking and listening). Give advice. Verify that advice is received in an appropriate manner, such as asking open-ended questions. Praising: During the previous check, praise the positive and avoid dismissing the negative in an unpleasant way (Jimbo, 2004).

Another method is a scientific statement. For example, you want to teach a diabetic patient how to take an insulin injection by himself. How? Explain the method. implementation in front of him. Make him perform in front of you. Nice debugging. Repeat the execution until you are sure that it is correct (Oyetunde & Akinmeyer, 2015).

Other methods include discussion, the necessity of having a dialogue moderator choose the topic of the session, prepare himself for it, and prepare a set of questions to be the focus of the discussion (Oyetunde & Akinmeyer, 2015).

The appropriate number is 12 - 8, preferably a homogeneous group (age - cultural - sometimes according to gender). Choose a quiet place - sit in a circle - the moderator sits with the group as if he is one of its members. The director begins by offering an interesting beginning to educate: it may be a movie or a group of pictures that direct people's minds to the focus of the discussion and understand the purpose of the dialogue (Oyetunde & Akinmeyer, 2015).

The manager asks questions and listens for answers, tries to activate the dialogue, and tries to benefit from the opinions of some to communicate the idea to others. End the session by summarizing the ideas and lessons learned (Oyetunde & Akinmeyer, 2015).

The main focus of health education for patients is the presence of communication skills. Communication skills include listening, without which there is no good communication. Possess the ability to sound trial. Use language appropriately: cyclical or comprehensible language - colloquial. The ability to understand and interpret non-verbal expressions: gestures and signs (Marcus, 2014).

The ability to attract and draw attention (likable character). Understand the nature of dialogue as general principles and accept the other opinion. Flexibility. The ability to interact with society and humility, and accept this society for what it is: for example, a person with a high personality who does not accept visiting simple poor people in their homes, cannot work in the field of communication with them and deliver a culturally appropriate message (Marcus, 2014).

Concept of family medicine practices

The family medicine system is the cornerstone of any serious attempt at health reform and of course it is the basis of the health insurance system as the family doctor is the doctor who starts the treatment journey with any patient of the family in the area he follows, and may complete the treatment of his patient if the disease is in the limits of his specialization in addition to increasing the level of his patient education, or transferring him to complete treatment with another specialized doctor (Rao & Prasad, 2018).

A well-known scientific equation, if its conditions are met, the result will be settled in favor of the citizens. The two sides of the equation are a well-qualified family doctor + some simple and cheap medicines + a simple laboratory in the health unit or family medicine center = the ability to treat diseases, and treatment of minor diseases as a result of the availability of patient as well as education. We will be able to avoid Serious complications that threaten the patient's life, and require more difficult and more expensive treatment, and its results are weaker! For example: follow-up and regular treatment of diseases of pressure and diabetes, which is easier and less expensive, and gives much better results than treatment of complications of pressure and diabetes (untreated) such as angina, stroke, brain hemorrhage, diabetic foot, kidney failure and others (Rao & Prasad, 2018).

The family medicine doctor is also able to pay attention early to diseases that need examinations and treatment above the simple capabilities of the health unit, where the health unit provides what is called "primary health care." The family doctor is qualified to determine the place to refer the patient when the higher specialized health care is needed, to the place where it provides the exact treatment that the disease needs, and

thus does not waste precious time because the patient is “lost” among many doctors and clinics that may be far from what his disease needs (Rao & Prasad, 2018).

We avoid delays, which often cause the condition to deteriorate and reduce recovery rates. Another important point is that the family doctor and primary health care units in turn prevent the flooding of advanced care places - such as university hospitals - with hundreds of simple cases, such as colds and stomach flu that can and must be treated efficiently in the nearest health unit to the patient, and of course this dumping weakens the ability of University hospitals to perform their primary role, in capturing and treating advanced cases, of which a good proportion of them are lost amid the deluge of simple cases (Rao & Prasad, 2018).

Role of family doctor in patient education

Family doctor or family medicine is a medical specialty that is considered one of the main medical specialties such as surgery, internal medicine, children and others. The doctor obtains this specialty after passing the fellowship or doctoral exam, after a training period of not less than four years, and the family doctor, family doctor, primary health care doctor, or General practitioners are all different names for one meaning and one goal, which is the application of the principle of comprehensive and continuous health care and provide patient education by gender, age or type of disease, a specialty that depends on health, behavioral and social sciences (Taylor, 2014).

The family doctor is the basic rule of the ideal and exemplary health pyramid, and from others it is not possible to establish a solid health system. How not, and it is the first line of defense to confront the disease, and the tasks of the family doctor are limited to him only and cannot be performed by others with other specialties, as his role is not limited to treating the disease in itself. Rather, it includes (Taylor, 2014):

1- Focusing on the patient as a single mass and a single organ (if an organ complains of it, the rest of the body responds to it with sleeplessness and fever), as the organs are linked to each other.

2- Dealing with the individual within the family with knowledge of prevention methods and the ability to diagnose and treat.

3- Achieving the connection with the patient within the family in all social and psychological aspects.

4- Knowledge of health problems in the community and the ability to set priorities.

5- Work to raise the health level of the individual, family and society through health education using various possible means.

6- Seeking to achieve community participation and coordination between the various relevant sectors in planning, organizing and evaluating health programs.

to other tasks.

As for what makes the family and community doctor distinct from others, it is his possession of an enormous amount of knowledge and skill, which made the gap wide between him and his peers with other medical specialties. The widening of his knowledge and his unlimited knowledge of various diseases, especially common diseases, chronic diseases and diseases with serious complications, made him distinguished (Taylor, 2014).

The family medicine doctor was also distinguished by his understanding and awareness of the opportunities, methods, and limits of prevention and early diagnosis. His awareness of the role of individual relationships within the family as a possible cause of health problems and the impact of disease on relationships within the family made him closer to the patient and the family, especially his awareness of the social and environmental conditions of his patients and how this affects the relationship between health and disease, as for his distinction Knowing the medical legislation, traditions and social customs and the extent of their impact on his patients made him aware of the health problems in the community (Hashim, 2016).

Unfortunately, many people, including educated people, still believe that the role of the family and community doctor is limited to referring the patient to the desired specialist, as he is nothing but an intermediary between him and the specialist doctor. They do not know that the family doctor is a specialist doctor who does not treat the individual only, but that his tasks go beyond that to include the family. The society and the diversity and multiplicity of its roles aims in the end to raise the level of health education of the individual, the family and society through the strong bond that binds him to the patient in addition to the other characteristics that made him distinct from others that I mentioned earlier (Hashim, 2016).

Results and discussion

By examining previous studies, it was found that there are many positive effects of patient education in the practices of the family doctor, which I will review below.

Educate and promote mental health

Mental health is like the rest of the body, as it can get tired and need treatment. Therefore, it is important to prevent and treat mental illnesses when they occur, and good mental health is linked to mental and psychological health, as it is responsible for human cognitive and emotional behaviors. From here we can define

mental health, which is an essential and indivisible part of health, and from this regard, the patient education affect on the level of mental health and family doctor has an important role in improving mental health of individuals (Keifi, Shahriari, Baghersad, Sheibani-Tehrani, & Rejalian, 2016).

Mental health is fundamental to the consolidation of our collective and individual ability to think, be affected, and interact with each other as human beings, earn a living and enjoy life. On this basis, the promotion, protection and restoration of mental health can be considered a vital concern of individuals, groups and societies around the world. Mental health is of great importance to the individual and society, as it cultivates happiness, stability and integration among individuals within the community. It also has an important role in choosing the right treatment methods for social problems that may affect the safety of the psychological growth process (Keifi, Shahriari, Baghersad, Sheibani-Tehrani, & Rejalian, 2016).

Recent studies have proven that psychological stress and anger are destructive factors for human health and psyche, and if the situation worsens, it may lead to serious diseases. Mental health may affect daily life, social relationships, as well as the physical health of individuals. On the other hand, daily stresses, personal connections, and physical health contribute to affecting mental health as well. Promoting mental health by the use of patient education and by the help of family doctor helps balance daily activities, responsibilities, and efforts (Keifi, Shahriari, Baghersad, Sheibani-Tehrani, & Rejalian, 2016).

The efforts made to achieve the goals, and this enables the person to enjoy his life and practice his activities naturally, so that he realizes his own capabilities, works productively, and is able to provide service to his community. It can help some people and may fail to help others, and the person may need medical advice to help determine the needs and the appropriate mental health promotion method for him ((Keifi, Shahriari, Baghersad, Sheibani-Tehrani, & Rejalian, 2016).

Ways to promote mental health include: Lifestyle changes such as stopping smoking, getting enough hours of sleep, and getting a balanced diet. Having a private time away from work stress to solve personal problems that affect mental health. Follow relaxation techniques such as meditation, deep breathing and mindfulness. Get emotional support from close people such as friends and family. Self-help, self-support and changing thought patterns. Other examples of mental patient education practices include (Keifi, Shahriari, Baghersad, Sheibani-Tehrani, & Rejalian, 2016):

- Stress and its prevention.
- Disease anxiety and its prevention.
- Depression and its prevention.

Educate and promote physical health

There are many aspects that patient education can help in with the help of the family doctor, the aspects and advices include the following: Walking daily: Walking daily for half an hour or an hour reduces the possibility of developing cancer

There is no need to hurry and speed: It is necessary to take time when doing daily chores to avoid exposure to high blood pressure. Make sure to eat vegetables and fruits at a rate of 3 daily servings in order to protect yourself from the risk of heart attack by 70% (An, Kim, Park, Moon, & Park, 2017).

Wear a good brand of sunglasses to provide you with protection from the sun's UV rays that can lead to cataracts or blindness in old age, so be careful when buying glasses to make sure of their good quality. Dental hygiene: for example, to avoid wetting the toothbrush with water before applying the paste to it, as a dry brush increases the possibility of getting rid of plaque by 67% (An, Kim, Park, Moon, & Park, 2017).

Sleep better, good sleep helps to combat premature aging and maintain youthful skin. Stop biting nails: This habit spoils the beauty of patient hands and may cause tiny cracks in the teeth, which increases the possibility of them getting cavities and may lead to small lacerations in the gums and may cause ulcers and infections.

Drink green tea: to have a cup of green tea daily, which prevents oxidation in the cells of the body, and reduces the possibility of cancer. All of these are some examples that patient educator can educate to patient in family medicine practices and help in the prevention of diseases in the long run (An, Kim, Park, Moon, & Park, 2017).

Other examples of physical health promotion and patient education about physical health include:

- Create awareness programs about diabetes and its prevention.
- Create awareness programs about hypertension and its prevention.
- Create awareness programs about obesity and its prevention.
- Create awareness programs about drugs and their prevention.

- Establishing awareness programs on early detection of chronic diseases.
- Create awareness programs about unhealthy eating habits and their prevention.
- Establishing awareness programs about increasing rates of physical activity or decreasing rates of physical activity and the diseases that cause both conditions.
- Establishing awareness programs about smoking, its control and prevention.
- Establishing awareness programs about breast cancer and all types of cancer and how to prevent it.
- Create awareness programs on all chronic diseases and healthy habits that must be followed to prevent them.

Building knowledge for community members and school students

The importance of patient education is mainly that it helps in building knowledge among community members and school students, increases their positive attitudes towards their health and teaches health skills necessary for a healthy life in schools, ministries, scientific and community institutions. The importance of patient education lies in that it motivates individuals to maintain their health and maintain it in the best way. patient education helps reduce risky behaviors, prevent disease and make healthy choices in their daily lives.

Helps increase people's knowledge and skills towards health. Maintains increased knowledge of physical, mental and emotional health and builds healthy individuals. Helps in spreading health terminology among individuals and society. Patient education reduces the risk of mental and emotional illnesses and prevents sexual diseases and family problems (See, Chan, Huggan, Tay, & Liaw, 2014).

Patient education for pregnant women

Knowing the importance of patient education for pregnant women is one of the important things that must be learned by the mother, in order to preserve her psychological and physical health and the health of her fetus, through practicing some health and psychological habits that help the pregnant woman to stay healthy and this is done through: Exercising Regularly an addition to prenatal care. Paying attention to nutrition and a balanced diet that helps the development of the fetus's brain well and an appropriate and healthy weight for the fetus during childbirth, and also reduces the risk of birth defects that the fetus may be exposed to and reduces the risk of anemia in the pregnant woman (See, Chan, Huggan, Tay, & Liaw, 2014).

Reducing symptoms that a pregnant woman may experience such as fatigue, morning sickness and vomiting. Awareness about the excess weight that a pregnant woman may be exposed to during pregnancy, as some women are concerned about the weight gain that they can gain during pregnancy, and it is important to discuss and review with the doctor constantly to know the normal weight and the mother's nutritional needs throughout pregnancy, and recommendations for women vary. Women who suffer from underweight before pregnancy and for others who suffer from obesity in addition to those who are carrying twins (See, Chan, Huggan, Tay, & Liaw, 2014).

Practicing healthy habits in case the pregnant woman is exposed to the most common diseases such as: colds, runny nose, upset stomach and getting rid of bad habits, by making the right choices for a healthy lifestyle that directly affects the health of the mother and fetus such as: stopping smoking, drug and alcohol abuse. Drinking alcohol during pregnancy is associated with several problems associated with the fetus (See, Chan, Huggan, Tay, & Liaw, 2014).

As drinking alcohol is transmitted to the fetus through the bloodstream and leads to fetal alcohol syndrome, which can cause a child to lose weight and cause a defect in the central nervous system, and drinking alcohol leads to complications during pregnancy such as: miscarriage, premature birth and stillbirth, As for smoking, it is considered dangerous during pregnancy, and smoking affects blood flow and oxygen delivery to the fetus, and affects the growth and birth of the fetus with a very low weight, and is the most common cause of death in the first weeks (See, Chan, Huggan, Tay, & Liaw, 2014).

Pre- and post-operative education

For example, there are preoperative instructions for adult patients:

- Patients who will undergo surgery during the morning period should not eat any food or drink after midnight on the night before the specified surgery. Patients who will have surgery in the afternoon should not eat any food or drink after 5:30 am on the same day they are scheduled to have their surgery. It includes foods such as: (dates and sweets) and drinks such as: (tea, coffee and soft drinks).
- A companion must be present with patient on the day of the operation, and he will be asked to wait in the hospital until the surgery is performed.
- Only one escort is allowed for each patient, and due to the short period of stay in the hospital, he will not be allowed to receive visitors.

- patients must clean their faces with a non-irritating lotion before coming to the hospital. For women, all traces of cosmetics should be removed and nail polish removed.
- They should not bring jewelry or valuable possessions and not bring large sums of cash with them when they come to the hospital, as the hospital is not responsible for losing any of these things.
- If they get prescriptions from the attending physician, they should go to the pharmacy and get the medications prescribed for them before the scheduled date for their surgery, as they must use these medications on time after their surgery.

They should bring all the medicines they are currently using in their original packages with the basic information on it (DeMarco, Nystrom, & Salvatore, 2011).

Improve patient satisfaction

Patient satisfaction will not only improve the patient experience but also correlate with better treatment outcomes. Patient satisfaction is a vital measure of quality service in healthcare systems as well as family medicine practices. Regarding family doctor, he should determine patient satisfaction begins with paying attention to patients and asking them about their concerns. Given that many healthcare companies do not conduct patient satisfaction surveys, The need to enhance patient satisfaction is an essential step in which modifications can enhance the overall patient experience (Farzianpour, Byravan, & Amirian, 2015). The main ways to enhance the patient experience are as follows:

1. Focus on the goal

It is imperative that the entire medical team including family doctor focus on why patients are here, and this requires a lot of training, as if each health worker understands their role and the purpose of having patients here, it will help enhance the patient experience. In other words, caring for the individual and listening to him and his needs is a priority for all hospitals and clinics.

2. Looking at things from the patient's eye

Basic ways to enhance patients' experience, one of them is to look at things from the patient's eye, which means that small things and details must be taken into account and attention to them in order to increase patient satisfaction.

Of course, this rule also includes the staff and the way they receive and deal with the patient. From the moment the patient enters the hospital or clinic, he begins to build his ideas around it. He must be received with a smile and always understood.

3. Inquiries about patients' complaints

It is important for all health workers to master the methods of dealing with patients and their complaints. It is necessary for the working person to try to provide the service in the best way without showing any signs that he does not know what the patient is asking for. It is important to ask him to understand what he wants. In the event that this person is unable to deal with the patient, it is important to connect him with another person who can meet his needs. Providing what the patient needs and understanding his needs saves a lot of trouble and increases patient satisfaction.

4. Apologize when needed

Although apologizing may be one of the most difficult things a person can do, it is essential that family doctor do it when needed, as it is among the basic ways to enhance the patient experience. If the patient's mood is disturbed by anything, the worker in front of him should apologize instead of justifying, this gives the patient comfort and a sense of concern.

5. Provide better medical care and patient education

It is essential for the patient to have the right medical care at all times, and providing that helps meet the needs of all patients. The patient must feel that the health facility is able to meet his needs, whether medical or psychological, without complaining, and this point specifically is among the basic ways that enhance the basic patient's experience.

Conclusion and recommendations

Public health goals can only be achieved with the positive participation of citizens, and this is done through patient education as well as doctors in the field of family medicine. Patient education (health education) is an educational process similar to the process of general education and aims to change information, attitudes, feelings and human behavior. Another definition is the process of translating known health facts into healthy behavioral patterns at the individual and community level, using modern educational methods.

Patient education goals include the following:

1. Changing concepts and values with regard to health and disease and making public health a goal for them.
2. Changing the attitudes, behavior and habits of citizens to enhance the health of the individual, family and society.

3. The success of health projects and units by organizing the community and confronting through the media.

Principles of patient education and its fields include the following. Personal health, home health, School health, Community health and education process. Health education methods and techniques include the media: It is the means used to communicate information and experiences to the masses of people, and it is characterized by helping the patient educator to communicate with a large number of people at the same time.

One of its most important shortcomings is that it does not involve the listener in planning the program, and its effectiveness may decrease. For reasons including: not access to the means, not attracting enough attention, unwillingness of the learner. Second: Coping methods: The educator interviews the patient. Third is personal conversation: For example, between the educator and the patient, the nurse and the mother, the social worker, the health aider.

Health classes: this method characterized by depend on specific topics for specific groups of learners, such as a course for mothers on child care, nutrition or bathing, a course for nursery supervisors on child care at nursery age, and a course on diabetes and how to treat it. Thus, the means of explanation are also used to attract attention. Meetings: Including discussion seminars, lectures, health committees, seminars and conferences.

The methods of confrontation are characterized by the following: Positive participation. Increasing compatibility with personal needs. Adaptation of roads according to circumstances. Clarity of experiences and emotions of the educator and the learner. Flexibility: it may be necessary to change the position.

Based on what was discussed during the research, the researcher recommends the following: Provide family doctors with knowledge of health information. Their use of social media and visual, audio and written media to spread health culture and patient education. Providing advice and health advice through the work of medical days. Providing health information to the sick individual in a manner different from the correct individual. Providing health information to the individual and society in an understandable and common manner based on the culture of the individual and society.

Communicate with the Ministry of Health to conduct health and educational campaigns capable of delivering information to the largest number of members of society. Therefore, family doctors and patient educators must follow effective means to provide health information to save society from distortions of information and apply it in its wrong form, thus affecting it negatively.

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